

stable upto 200°. The pure and dried complex was analysed for niobium by ignition of a weighed portion to niobium pentoxide. The carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen contents were estimated by the usual combustion methods. The niobium complex was found to have the composition $\text{NbO}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2\text{N})_3$ (Found : Nb, 9.71 ; C, 67.98 ; N, 4.23, H, 6.39%. Calcd. Nb, 9.71 ; C, 67.84 ; N, 4.40 ; H, 6.33%).

The tantalum complex was of indefinite composition. It lost weight as the temperature was increased and ultimately converted to the pentoxide at 500°. The complex was insoluble in all the solvent mentioned above.

Effect of pH: Niobium and tantalum were precipitated and determined at different pH following the general procedure described earlier. The results indicated that the precipitation of niobium and tantalum was quantitative in the pH range 4.0 – 6.0 and 0.5 – 1.5 respectively.

Effect of foreign ions: The following ions did not interfere : 200 mg each of alkali metals, Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II), Be(II), Zn(II), Cr(III), La(III), Ca(III), Mg(II), Al(III), Hg(II), Cd(II), Bi(III), acetate, citrate and carbonate ; 100 mg of V(IV), Th(IV), Ce(III), Zr(IV) and U(VI) ; 50 mg of Mo(IV) and W(VI). However, in the case of niobium, Ti(IV) interfered and Zr(IV) and Ce(IV) had to be masked by EDTA. In determination of tantalum, Ti(IV) and Zr(IV) had to be masked by fluoride and EDTA ; Mo(IV) and W(VI) caused interference.

Separation of niobium and tantalum: The pH of the solution was adjusted to 4.5 – 5.5 with 20% ammonium acetate or 10% (v/v) sulphuric acid and niobium was precipitated by slow addition of 2% alcoholic solution of the reagent (10 ml for every 10 mg of metal). The precipitate was digested over hot water bath and niobium was determined as described earlier. The filtrate obtained from the separation of niobium was evaporated to about 200 ml. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 0.5 – 1.5 and the solution was heated to 60°. Tantalum was then precipitated and determined as described earlier.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their gratitude to Prof. S. G. Tandon for providing facilities in the Department. One of them (B. S. C) is thankful to U. G. C., New Delhi for the award of fellowship.

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Electrochromatographic Studies of Metal Ions on Sn(IV) Hexacyanoferrate(II) Papers : Separation of Metal Ions

K. G. VARSHNEY and A. A. KHAN

Chemistry Section, Z. H. College of Engg. & Tech., Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh

and

J. B. JAIN

Chemistry Department, Hindu College, Moradabad

Manuscript received 29 February 1980, revised 13 March 1981, accepted 14 August 1981

METAL hexacyanoferrates(II) have shown promising characteristics as inorganic ion exchangers¹⁻³. They have been utilized in column^{4,5} and paper⁶ chromatography of metal ions. However, a systematic electrochromatographic study of the common metal ions on papers impregnated with such materials is still lacking. The present paper summarizes our study on Sn(IV) hexacyanoferrate (II) papers which has resulted in some important binary separations.

Experimental

Apparatus: Electrochromatographic studies were performed on Whatman No. 1 paper strips of size 46.4 × 2.5 cm on a horizontal strip apparatus with a regulated power supply.

Preparation of the ion exchange papers: The paper strips were dipped in a 0.1M aqueous solution of Sn(IV) chloride for a few seconds. After drying on a filter paper they were dipped in a 0.1M aqueous solution of $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ and dried again at room temperature. They were then washed thoroughly in distilled water to remove excess reagents. The strips were finally dried and used as such.

Procedure: The electrophoresis was performed as usual⁷ by taking the various solutions as background electrolytes. The time of migration was fixed as 6 hrs and the potential applied was 100 volts in each case.

Separations achieved: Table 1 summarizes the separations achieved on these papers based on the migration difference.

TABLE 1 — METAL ION SEPARATIONS ACHIEVED IN DIFFERENT ELECTROLYTES ON Sn (IV) HEXACYANOFERRATE (II) PAPERS

Electrolyte used	Separation achieved
0.1 M Tartaric acid	Bi-Tl Hg-Tl Ba and Tl from numerous metal ions.
0.1 M Oxalic acid	Se-Mo, Te-Mo, UO_2^{2+} -Mo, Cr-Mo, In-La.
0.1 M Acetic acid	Ba and Sr from numerous metal ions.

Results and Discussion

These studies reveal some interesting features. Some metal ions were taken for their electrochromatographic study in selected media namely 0.1M aqueous

solutions of oxalic, citric, tartaric, acetic and formic acids as electrolytes. The mobility of metal ions is mainly governed by the following three factors: (i) complex formation between the electrolyte and the metal ion, (ii) the ion exchange behaviour of the inorganic material and (iii) the electric field applied.

The acids mentioned above were selected as the background electrolytes mainly because they form complexes with metals.

The presence of an ion exchange material on paper obviously modified the movement of the metal ions. It was clear from a comparison of the migration of metal ions on plain and impregnated papers that the migration was different in the two cases thus suggesting the formation of a coating of the ion exchange material on papers. Also, a quantitative determination of the Sn(IV) and Fe(II) ions in the solution obtained after dissolving the impregnated strips in $\text{HNO}_3\text{-HClO}_4$ mixture gave the same ratio of these two ions as obtained earlier in the synthetic study⁷ of Sn(IV) hexacyanoferrate(II). This confirmed the above conclusion. The mobility greatly decreased on impregnated papers probably because of the ion exchange and the adsorption phenomena taking place simultaneously. A comparison of the migration behaviour in all the electrolytes used revealed the following sequence: formic acid > acetic acid > tartaric acid > citric acid > oxalic acid. This was also the order of complex forming ability of these acids.

An effect of electric field on the migration of metal ions is evident from the difference in the results

obtained in these studies and a paper chromatographic study⁶ made separately.

Using this very simple technique, a large number of good separations have become possible as shown in Table I. These separations are important from the analytical point of view. To mention a few, Bi-Tl, $\text{Hg}^+\text{-Tl}$, $\text{Hg}^{++}\text{-Tl}$, Se-Mo, $\text{UO}_2\text{-Mo}$, Cr-Mo and In-La have been achieved on impregnated papers. Plain papers have also effected separations such as Au-Cu-Pt, Ag-Cu-Tl, Hg-Cd, Zn-La, Ni-Co and Th-Tl thus showing the usefulness of the electrolytes employed in these studies.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. R. N. Gupta for research facilities. Financial assistance of the U.G.C. and C.S.I.R. is gratefully acknowledged.

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